

Rotating Optical Observatory for Extreme Measuring Efficiency and Rigour

ROEMER

Proposal for the Third Medium Size ESA Mission (M3)

A mission dedicated to very accurate astrometric
and photometric measurement of 10^8 stars

U. Bastian, G. Gilmore, J.L. Halbwachs, E. Høg, J. Knude,
J. Kovalevsky, A. Labeyrie, F. van Leeuwen, L. Lindegren,
J.W. Pel, H. Schrijver, R. Stabell and P. Thejll

Edited by L. Lindegren

Lund 1993

The Danish astronomer OLE RØMER (1644–1710) is best known as the discoverer of the speed of light. Around 1675, while working at the newly created Royal Observatory in Paris, he noticed that the intervals between successive eclipses of Jupiter's moons were not always in agreement with the ephemerides that had recently been calculated by Cassini. Depending on the relative motion of Earth and Jupiter the intervals were sometimes larger, sometimes smaller. Rømer correctly inferred that these discrepancies were due to the finite time it took for light to travel from Jupiter to Earth. He computed a value of 22 minutes for the time it takes light to travel one diameter of the Earth orbit. Not knowing this diameter with any reliability he did not calculate the speed of light in terrestrial units.

After his return to Copenhagen in 1681, Rømer constructed a series of instruments for measuring the positions of celestial bodies. His instruments gradually incorporated several new and ingenious concepts which were perfected during the next two centuries: the use of a long axis resting on two bearings for better definition of the viewing plane; microscopic reading of a graduated full circle; the use of counterweights to reduce flexure; and an emphasis on symmetrical design and measuring principles to eliminate otherwise uncontrollable errors. His *rota meridiana* constructed in 1704 is the prototype for the modern meridian circle, even today one of the most efficient and accurate instruments for ground-based positional measurements. Rømer's strive for ever improved accuracy may have been motivated by the search for stellar parallax. This phenomenon, the ultimate proof of the Copernican theory, would however elude astronomers for yet another century.

All Rømer's instruments and all the observations except those from three nights called *triduum* were destroyed in the fire of 1728. The *triduum* observations of 88 stars were used in 1756 by Tobias Mayer together with his own observations to discover that a fourth of the stars showed a significant change of position, thus deriving the first proper motions of stars from modern observations.

ROEMER

Proposal for the Third Medium Size ESA Mission (M3)

Contents

Executive Summary	1
Main Mission Characteristics	2
1. Introduction	3
2. Scientific Objectives	4
2.1. Stellar structure	4
2.2. Stellar evolution and the cosmic distance scale	7
2.3. Stellar kinematics	7
2.4. Double stars and unseen companions	11
2.5. Solar system objects	11
2.6. General relativity	12
2.7. Reference frame	13
3. Payload Concept	14
3.1. Basic considerations	14
3.2. Detection system	15
3.3. Optical system	18
3.4. Consequences for the spacecraft design	19
3.5. Towards 10 micro-arcsec astrometry: The FIZEAU option	20
4. Mission and System Aspects	21
4.1. Predicted performance	21
4.2. Mission requirements	23
4.3. Technological development requirements	24
4.4. Mass budget	24
5. Science Operations, Data Reductions and Archiving	25
6. Management and Funding	27
7. References	27
List of Proposers	28
Acknowledgement	28

Annexes (edited by E. Høg)

Annex A

Scientific Objectives (10 pages)

Annex B

Payload, Operations and Performance (55 pages)

The Annexes are not generally distributed with this Proposal. They contain the unabridged contributions of the proposers from which the present document was assembled, as well as technical papers which for various reasons could not be included here. To obtain copies of the Annexes, please contact:

Prof. E. Høg
Copenhagen University Observatory
Østervoldgade 3
DK-1350 Copenhagen K, Denmark

Telephone: (45) 35 323975
FAX: (45) 35 323989
Telex: 44155 DANAST DK
E-mail: erik@astro.ku.dk

Additional copies of the ROEMER Proposal can be obtained from:

Dr. L. Lindegren
Lund Observatory
Box 43
S-22100 Lund, Sweden

Telephone: (46) 46 107309
FAX: (46) 46 104614
Telex: 33199 OBSNOT S
E-mail: lennart@astro.lu.se

Executive Summary

The proposed ROEMER mission aims at the first high-accuracy astrometric and photometric survey of faint stars. Based on the well-proven concepts of Hipparcos, but employing a vastly superior detection system, ROEMER could measure some 100 million stars down to 18th magnitude, including all the 50 million stars brighter than $V = 15.5$. A 2.5-year mission yields the positions, absolute trigonometric parallaxes and annual proper motions with an accuracy in the range of 0.1 milli-arcsec ($V \leq 11$) to 1.5 milli-arcsec ($V = 17$), and magnitudes in five wavelength bands to an accuracy of 0.001 to 0.02 mag.

The scientific objectives include a thorough improvement of the current knowledge of stellar structure and evolution, stellar dynamics, star clusters and associations, unseen companions, the galactic and cosmological distance scales, and solar-system dynamics. The mission will establish an inertial optical reference frame several times better than currently achieved with radio observations and directly tied to the extragalactic frame. With an average density of 70 stars in a 10×10 arcmin² field this reference frame will be directly accessible to large ground-based telescopes.

Basic mission concepts, as proposed by Høg (1992), are derived from the highly successful Hipparcos mission. Like its predecessor, ROEMER is conceived as a free-flying, three-axis controlled satellite in geostationary orbit, with a modest optical telescope continuously sweeping across the sky in a pre-defined pattern. Two widely separated viewing directions provide the large-angle measurement capability necessary to build a globally rigid astrometric system.

ROEMER is however much more than a mere replication of Hipparcos. The use of several CCDs directly in the focal plane, with their higher quantum efficiency, smaller transmission losses and capability to observe thousands of stars strictly simultaneously, provides a measuring system which is at least 10^5 times more efficient than Hipparcos in terms of photon utilization. This translates into 20 times smaller errors, five magnitudes fainter limit, and a thousand times more programme stars—noting that Hipparcos is already achieving orders-of-magnitude improvement over previous knowledge. The inclusion of colour filters for several wavelength bands, from near-UV to near-IR, adds tremendously to the astrophysical value of the mission. While the need for highly stable solid-state detectors cooled to -70° C may raise a technological challenge, it also represents a major simplification of the payload in terms of fewer mechanisms, no starmapper attitude sensors, no relay optics, built-in redundancy, and easier calibration and operation.

The optical telescope has two half-circular openings with a diameter of 34 cm. Matching the diffractive resolution to the smallest available CCD pixel width (about $4 \mu\text{m}$) implies a focal length of nearly 5 m. This can be accommodated in a 3 m diameter cylindrical spacecraft by means of two folding mirrors. A Wright-Väisälä optical system provides diffraction-limited images in a flat field of one degree diameter. A very smooth rotation with a period of about 2 hours is assured by a rigid spacecraft structure with minimum perturbations from solar radiation pressure and gyroscopes—the latter not being used at all during science operations. The attitude control system is based on cold-gas thrusters to be fired at intervals of approximately 30 min. A rotationally symmetric, compact shape of the satellite, as illustrated on the front cover, will best satisfy these requirements.

It is envisaged that the satellite is designed, built, launched and operated under the direct responsibility of ESA. The preparation of the observing programme and the analysis of the science data would however be undertaken by a special team of scientists for which national funding will be sought.

Main Characteristics of the ROEMER Mission

Expected results

number of stars	100 million
limiting magnitude	$V = 18$
completeness limit	$V = 15.5$ (50 million stars)
accuracy of positions and parallaxes	0.1 mas ($V \leq 11$) to 1.3 mas ($V \simeq 17$)
accuracy of proper motions	0.1 mas/yr ($V \leq 11$) to 1.5 mas/yr ($V \simeq 17$)
systematic errors	< 0.1 mas
photometric accuracy	0.001 mag ($V \leq 11$) to 0.016 mag ($V \simeq 17$)
photometric colour bands	(e.g.) U, B, V, R, I , plus a wide band (W) and polarization filters ($P+, P-$)

Payload

optical system	all-reflective, folded Wright-Väisälä
telescope aperture diameter	336 mm
telescope focal length	4700 mm
field of view	1.4° diameter
angle between viewing directions	$\sim 54.5^\circ$
detection system	20 CCDs cooled to -70° C
number of pixels	$4096 \times 1024 + 256 \times 64$
pixel size	$4 \times 16 \mu\text{m}^2 + 4 \times 256 \mu\text{m}^2$
wavelength band	300–950 nm
payload mass	215 kg

System

mission duration	2.5 yr (consumables: 5 yr)
orbit	geostationary
power source	fixed solar panels (7 m ²)
attitude control	cold gas thrusters
spin rate	170 arcsec/s (127 min period)
angle from spin axis to the Sun	55°
precession of spin axis about the Sun	73 day period
nominal motion of spin axis on sky	$4.1^\circ \text{ day}^{-1}$
scientific telemetry rate	50 kbytes/s
external dimensions of satellite	$\text{Ø } 3.0 \text{ m} \times 3.5 \text{ m}$ (cylindrical)
launch mass	1140 kg
mass in geostationary orbit	640 kg

1. Introduction

Physical sciences evolve through the continual confrontation of theory with empirical data. In Astronomy, through the combined efforts over many decades of theoreticians, observers and experimenters, a reasonably coherent picture has been formed encompassing the very early history of the Universe, the formation of large-scale structures, galaxies, stars and planets, nucleosynthesis and the origin of atomic elements. The picture is by no means complete, and important experiments are designed to address specific questions within this general framework.

There is however another type of experiment which is not primarily aimed at solving some particular problem, but rather to explore the rich complexity of Nature in order to find new patterns, anomalies and even contradictions to established concepts. This is the spirit of the proposed ROEMER mission.

The European Space Agency's astrometry mission Hipparcos, launched in 1989, is now achieving the targetted 2 milli-arcsec (mas) astrometric accuracy for most of its programme of 118,000 stars brighter than $V = 12.7$ (Perryman et al. 1992). The success of Hipparcos has shown the conceptual validity of a *small scanning astrometry satellite*, reaching a global angular accuracy far exceeding the resolution of the instrument, and for a number of objects limited only by practical considerations and detector efficiency. Although the scientific analysis of the results of Hipparcos has not even started, it is clear that the mission represents an order-of-magnitude improvement over current knowledge in many areas of astronomy and astrophysics.

The ROEMER satellite, first proposed by Høg (1992), will observe 100 million stars with an astrometric accuracy in the range from 0.1 to 1.5 mas and determine the magnitudes in five colour bands with an accuracy of 0.001 to 0.02 mag. Among the most obvious and immediate results are:

- absolute trigonometric parallaxes yielding stellar distances within a volume of several kpc^3 around the sun;
- multi-colour photometry for the same stars enabling the determination of luminosities, temperatures, metallicities, and interstellar extinction;
- proper motions in a inertial reference frame directly tied to galaxies and quasars;
- a full-sky network of astrometric reference stars and photometric standards with sufficient density and magnitude range to be directly accessible in the small fields of large ground-based telescopes.

With its very broad scientific scope and ability to probe directly a sizable fraction of the Galaxy, ROEMER is likely to revolutionize much of our understanding of the formation, structure and evolution of stars and stellar systems.

The rationale for the ROEMER payload takes its origin in such scientific requirements and in lessons from the Hipparcos mission. One important lesson is that photometry in several wavelength bands should be an integral part of the mission. In the first place a colour index must be obtained for all programme stars in order to determine and correct for an expected effect of chromaticity in the optical system. But photometric measurements in (say) five colour bands with 0.01 mag accuracy are also by themselves of extremely high scientific value. Another lesson is that the various torques acting on the satellite must be reduced in order to enable longer periods of free satellite rotation. This can be achieved with proper design and by obliterating the need for gyroscopes in normal operation.

4 Scientific Objectives

The drastic improvement in accuracy, sensitivity and number of objects for the ROEMER mission, as compared with Hipparcos, is achieved almost entirely through the use of very efficient CCD detectors directly in the focal plane. This replaces the complicated focal plane assembly of Hipparcos, with its modulating grid, switching mirror mechanism, relay optics, calibration mechanisms, image dissector tubes, dichroic mirrors and photomultipliers. The higher quantum efficiency, smaller transmission losses and the simultaneous observation of thousands of stars translate into a twentyfold increase in accuracy, a 100 times fainter photon limit and a 1000 times more objects. This is achieved with an optical instrument of about the same size as Hipparcos and involving no additional critical subsystems apart from the detectors. We are therefore confident that the ROEMER mission, in terms of overall complexity, size and cost, compares favourably with Hipparcos.

We estimate that 0.1 mas ($5 \cdot 10^{-10}$ rad) is the practical limit of accuracy that can be reached with a small scanning satellite like ROEMER. For another order-of-magnitude improvement it would be necessary to increase the intrinsic resolution of the instrument by a corresponding factor, e.g., in the form of an optical interferometer with a baseline of several metres. Previous concepts for space interferometers have been pointing instruments capable of making relative measurements of rather few objects but with very high accuracy. In Section 3.5 we briefly outline some ideas for a mission (FIZEAU) which combines the interferometric concept with the notion of a scanning, survey-type satellite for global astrometric and photometric measurements. Such a mission would open entirely new and very exciting vistas, but is clearly beyond the scope of this proposal.

2. Scientific Objectives

2.1. Stellar structure

The basic astrometric quantity that is crucial for all of astrophysics is the parallax. This is because the parallax can provide the only truly independent means to transform apparent parameters into physical quantities expressed in terrestrial units. Three such quantities are essential inputs to the modelling of a star: its luminosity, mass and radius.

2.1.1. *Luminosities (absolute magnitudes)*

Apparent magnitudes express the number of photons reaching the Earth. They become absolute magnitudes, a measure of the total luminosity in the spectral range defined by the photometric system, if one knows the distances that is to say the parallaxes. Stellar interior modelling actually uses bolometric absolute magnitudes, but these can be derived using theoretical considerations involving the spectral types of stars. The bolometric magnitude is a measure of the actual total energy output and an essential parameter for models of the internal structure of stars.

The requirement for accuracy in the inputs of stellar models is of the order of 1%, for which parallaxes accurate to 0.5% are needed. [Today, such accurate luminosities, if available, could not be fully utilized because the chemical composition of the stars is usually not known to a matching accuracy. That can however be expected two decades from now when ROEMER parallaxes will come into use.] The reddening correction, for which the five-channel photometry will provide the information, has to reach an accuracy of better

Table 1. Predicted numbers of stars per spectral type and absolute magnitude for which the accuracy of the parallax will be better than 0.5% for a 2.5 year ROEMER mission. Column 1 gives the absolute magnitude, columns 2 to 7 the number of stars as derived from Allen (1973) and expected accuracies for the ROEMER mission.

M_V	B	A	F	G	K	M
-5	0	0	0	0	0	0
-4	0	0	0	0	0	0
-3	0	0	0	0	0	0
-2	1	0	0	0	0	0
-1	7	1	1	1	1	2
0	10	10	1	4	13	5
1	16	52	16	16	63	5
2	10	105	84	26	58	0
3	5	42	367	79	52	0
4	0	16	628	367	52	0
5	0	0	314	1047	157	0
6	0	0	105	785	785	5
7	0	0	52	419	1571	52
8	0	0	2	85	530	212
9	0	0	0	42	318	637
10	1	0	0	0	26	524
11	7	2	1	0	13	589
12	4	8	2	0	2	188
13	8	11	6	2	8	188
14	2	3	3	2	2	26
15	4	5	3	4	3	21
16	2	3	2	2	0	4

than 0.01 magnitudes. ROEMER will give a parallax accuracy of 0.5% for stars brighter than $V = 11$ in a sphere of 50 pc, assuming a 2.5 year mission, and within 80 pc for a five year mission (cf. Table 2, p. 22). Of course many stars will get a much better precision.

Important categories of stars have many representatives in such spheres, so that current uncertainties in their energy outputs will be resolved. Even many rarer type stars, such as supergiants, T Tauris and RR Lyraes, will get individual luminosity calibrations to a level of 5%. Table 1 shows the number of stars per spectral type and absolute magnitude interval, for which a parallax accuracy of better than 0.5% is expected.

To take a more specific example, the accuracy of ROEMER is required to obtain 1% relative precision for the luminosities of a sizable number of main sequence stars of spectral type A and F. This group is especially interesting for internal structure models because it contains many stars with peculiar spectral features, the transition from convective to radiative energy transport in the envelope, and the pulsating δ Scuti stars. The 2.5 year mission will provide some 225 main sequence A-type stars with errors of less than 0.01 on the absolute magnitudes. Similarly, around 1500 main sequence F-type stars will be equally well determined. For a five year mission these numbers are four times larger, while for a 2% accuracy on the luminosities eight times as many stars can be expected.

6 Scientific Objectives

With metallicity obtained by spectroscopic observations, a very precise determination of the luminosity will allow fundamental parameters such as the depth of the convective zone and the efficiency of the convective transport to be derived. For cooler stars, precise luminosity determinations will put strong constraints on other fundamental parameters such as the equation of state and, for the coolest ones, molecular opacities. The additional high-precision photometry will be of benefit here. A 2.5 year mission would provide around 2400 M dwarfs with less than 0.5% errors on the distances.

2.1.2. *Stellar masses*

The knowledge of fundamental stellar masses is derived mainly from the analysis of double stars. The ROEMER mission will determine magnitudes and relative positions of the components of double stars, and its contribution to the determination of stellar masses will be very large. At present, the best-determined masses are those obtained from the analysis of eclipsing variables. Many of them are not representative of single stars because they are so close to each other that mass exchange may occur or have occurred in the past, and their evolutionary track is therefore biased. Hipparcos will provide some results on the masses of separated couples. However, the parallax uncertainties will severely limit their number, and for many classes of stars there will still not be a single good mass available. This is a very strong impediment to the physical study of the interiors and evolution of these stars.

With its 20 times more accurate parallaxes, ROEMER will considerably increase the number of known orbital binaries for which the parallax is good enough to give their masses. In addition, using the photometric measurements, the mass–luminosity relations should be considerably improved (in particular for low mass stars for which it is presently very uncertain). This improvement will lead to the possibility of estimating the masses of other double or single stars by means of the mass–luminosity relations with a few percent accuracy, since the effect of parallax errors is considerably reduced when one uses this relation.

2.1.3. *Stellar radii*

Only few accurate radii are available for testing stellar models. Again, the best-determined radii at present are obtained from the analysis of eclipsing variables. Ground-based interferometry and lunar occultation techniques typically give angular radii with accuracies in the range 0.2 to 2 mas. Even for the apparently largest stars this represents a relative error of at least a few percent. Precisely because of this lack of precision, it is essential that in the transformation into absolute dimensions of the star additional errors due to the parallax are minimized. Most of the presently well-determined stellar diameters correspond to giants and supergiants. Although they are bright, they are still distant. For instance, the distance of Betelgeuse, a red supergiant well observed by visual and infrared interferometry, is about 200 pc. Hipparcos will give its distance to 20% while ROEMER will determine it with 2% accuracy: this is what is needed to meet current requirements. The fact that one shall get the absolute dimensions and their time variations at different wavelengths in absolute units is very important for the understanding of the physics. This is particularly true for the various pulsating variables such as Miras, RV Tauri and W Virginis stars.

2.2. Stellar evolution and the cosmic distance scale

The high accuracy proper motions and parallaxes obtainable with the ROEMER mission make it possible to derive for a wide range of open clusters and associations clearly defined member stars as well as very well-determined distances. For an average system of 200 members, the parallax accuracy of the system is perhaps six times better than for the individual member stars. As stars in open clusters and associations are of closely the same age and composition, these groups are ideal for establishing a range of well-determined isochrones. The homogeneous set of photometric data will provide the systematic corrections for reddening as well as some information on metallicity variations. Subsequent comparisons with theoretical isochrones will serve two purposes: a thorough check on their validity in the details, which reflects the validity of assumptions made in stellar structure modelling, and providing a calibration of empirical isochrones to an evolutionary time scale. At this point it may well become possible to calibrate ages for numerous individual field stars in the solar neighbourhood.

Only when the effects of age and metallicity on the absolute magnitudes of stars are understood and quantified, can we proceed and extrapolate to objects outside the range of direct parallax measurement. Many of these objects are important distance calibrators themselves, and some will get their parallax measured directly, albeit with only a 5–10% accuracy. The main help comes again from star clusters, in this case both galactic and globular clusters, as even for nearby stars with very accurate parallaxes the relation between age and absolute magnitude cannot be determined independently. The problem thus reduces to a familiar one: fitting the photometric data of a number of star clusters containing other distance calibrators to the now much more detailed HR diagram based on clusters and associations for which accurate distances and metallicities have been measured. Such a calibration, which currently still has an uncertainty of around 0.3 magnitudes, can with ROEMER data reach an accuracy close to 0.01 magnitudes, thus improving the quality of indirect distance measurements to a level of 1 percent and better.

The ROEMER mission will contribute very significantly to the study of post-main-sequence evolution: absolute magnitudes can be obtained for giants, supergiants, horizontal branch stars, hot subdwarfs and white dwarfs. In the case of white dwarfs the determination of luminosities can be used to derive masses and ages, which will provide important information on the minimum age of the Galaxy, and on the spread in masses of white dwarfs. The survey will also include large numbers of possible white dwarfs, and provide an increase by more than a factor ten of the number of white dwarfs presently known. Distances and luminosities for hot subdwarfs will allow further constraints on the theories of the late stages of stellar evolution.

2.3. Stellar kinematics

The astrometric and photometric survey of all stars brighter than $V = 15.5$ is an excellent basis for systematic statistical studies of stellar properties and kinematics, which avoids much of the selection biases present in existing catalogues. For the fainter stars down to the limiting magnitude of ROEMER, a truly random (and thus unbiased) sample can be defined if a part of the observing programme is drawn from a complete inventory of all the stars brighter than the 18th magnitude. This is feasible by means of existing or planned digitised photographic sky surveys.

8 Scientific Objectives

2.3.1. *Evolution of the Galaxy and its dark matter*

There are several fundamental aspects of the structure of galaxies which can be determined reliably only in the Milky Way Galaxy. Some of these properties of the Galaxy retain a fossil record of the conditions in the early universe at the time of galaxy formation (e.g., the present distribution of angular momentum), others are determined by the important physical processes during galaxy formation (e.g., correlations between chemical abundance and kinematics in old stars), while others again are determined by the distribution of the apparently ubiquitous ‘missing’ mass (e.g., the combination of stellar kinematics and the shape of the stellar system). Other properties of the Milky Way are determined by its later evolution. For example, if the Galaxy halo formed primarily by mergers of dwarf galaxies in which star formation had already begun, as predicted by standard Cold Dark Matter cosmologies, then substructure in kinematic phase space will exist. Thus, detailed analysis of the kinematics, chemical abundances, and spatial distribution of old stars in the Milky Way Galaxy provides a powerful means to study the important physical processes which dominated the early stages of the formation and evolution of galaxies, and the spatial distribution and nature of the missing mass.

2.3.2. *Stellar kinematics and chemical abundances*

The scale lengths and shape of any galaxy are determined by its gravitational potential and stellar kinematics. In an equilibrium, axisymmetric system, the kinematics are describable by three orthogonal components of the velocity dispersion and one non-zero mean streaming motion (rotation). The velocity dispersions provide three-dimensional pressure support against gravity, while the angular momentum of the streaming provides support in the radial direction, perpendicular to the angular momentum vector. However, many combinations of these quantities can correspond to the same shape and size of a single galaxy, given a potential. Since it is the product of scale length and velocity dispersion that combines with the angular momentum to balance the gravitational force, and it is only this product which is observable in external galaxies (due to integration of kinematics down the line-of-sight through the galaxy), it is impossible in principle to determine uniquely the kinematical distribution function of external galaxies. One requires independent determination of the stellar density profile and kinematics, which is possible only for the Milky Way Galaxy.

An observational data set appropriate for analysis of the true kinematic, dynamic, and stellar population structure of the Galaxy is readily defined. One requires a complete sampling of a sufficiently large volume of space so that the full phase space distribution function can be determined with sufficient precision to measure the small deviations from symmetry which are sensitive to the nature of dark matter and the evolutionary history of the Galaxy. Such a sampling must extend beyond a half-mass radius of the dark halo for a subset of kinematic and abundance tracers, where luminous halo giants are ideal. It must extend to a thick disk scale height, to sample the main sequence of the dominant old high angular momentum stellar population. It must extend radially by a thin disk scale length, so that local kinematics can be disentangled from global dynamics. It must sample giants in the galactic warp, so that deviations from axi-symmetry can be measured, by averaging systematic motions over suitable volumes. An ideal sample is that proposed for ROEMER, since each of these requirements corresponds to a reliable sample out to an apparent magnitude of about $V = 15$. Given such a data set, one could solve the following fundamental problems.

The shape of dark matter halos and the disk–halo conspiracy What is the shape of galactic halos? This is difficult to answer observationally, since at best one can measure only the gravitational potentials of dark halos, and potentials (at large distances from the centre) are more spherical than are the generating mass distributions. In external galaxies one is further limited since kinematics provide only a projection of the true three-dimensional data, and the information may be inherently degenerate. A related point is the disk–halo conspiracy, in which the disk and dark halo balance to produce a flat rotation curve. Both these problems may be studied using the large-scale dynamics of the galactic disk and stellar halo. Detailed N -body work suggests that dark halos are tri-axial and have cores. Disk stability and rotation curve modelling, together with local disk mass density determinations, are sensitive to both halo core properties and halo shape. Stellar halo kinematics provide an additional constraint. In combination these data will determine the intrinsic shape of the dark matter halo.

The Warp, and deviations from axi-symmetry Disks tend to be warped, especially when seen in the 21 cm line. No useful data exist on stellar warps, and little useful dynamics is possible without stellar data, since only stars are free of hydrodynamical complications. The most likely cause of warps is a large-scale instability driven by deviations from axi-symmetry in the mass distribution. Such deviations provide a unique clue to the nature of the dark matter, and its dissipational history. The dynamical signal of a warp is weak, but would be seen as correlated flow patterns or corrugations in the stellar velocity field, rather like the ripples in a butterfly's wings. This would be detectable in a large body of precise kinematic data with a reliably determined reference frame over the whole sky. Such data would also uniquely determine the extent to which deviations from axi-symmetry, including both spiral structure and possible large scale ellipticity of the disk, are generated by local gravitational effects or by dynamical instabilities on a larger scale. This is the unique test of disk dynamical evolutionary models, and is also crucial for interpretation of rotation curves in external galaxies.

Do galaxies form from Cold Dark Matter lumps? The enduring puzzle in cosmology is to know if galaxies form from many small structures or a few large ones. (More elegantly, what is the power spectrum of perturbations on galactic scales in the early Universe?) If the Milky Way formed from the bottom up, as Cold Dark Matter cosmologies predict, there will be residual structure in kinematic phase space visible as a fossil remnant of the merger history of the Galaxy. Such remnants will now fill dispersion orbits, and will be detectable in very large and high-quality data sets as deviations from a smooth phase space distribution function.

Is there dark matter in galactic disks? If dark matter is baryonic it could dissipate, and be found in small structures such as a galactic disk. While near the Sun one now knows there is no significant dark matter, near the galactic centre, at very low angular momenta, and in the outer disk, with very high angular momenta, we have no robust information. This could be obtained from precise distance and proper motion data. One could in effect duplicate the local determinations of the vertical disk force law at several radii, and provide a reliable and direct determination of the radial distribution of mass in the disk. Such information would uniquely test the existence of dissipational dark matter, and would determine the disk dynamical stability on length scales ideal for testing present understanding of the dynamical evolution of disk structure, particularly spiral structure.

The rotation curve ROEMER data would determine the rotation curve to sufficient precision to provide a reliable mass model of the halo, to discriminate between gas dynamical and gravitational dynamical origin of structure in the rotation curve, and to determine the pressure-gravity balance supporting the old stars of the galactic thick disk and halo. Sufficient information would be available to allow a full phase space distribution function analysis of galactic dynamics, and for the first time allow simple moment approximations to be superseded. This would provide the first opportunity to deduce the physics of those processes which populate the phase space distribution function with stars, or in approximate terms, to determine the physics of the formation, evolution, and present structure of a major spiral galaxy.

2.3.3. *Studies of F and G stars in the galactic disk*

Galactic studies using the combination of space motions and chemical composition have made evident that an understanding of the galactic disk requires insight in the kinematics as well as the chemistry. Earlier beliefs that a homogeneous relation existed between the two parameter sets are now doubted. The hypothesis that velocity dispersions increase and metal content decreases with stellar age does not always hold.

Despite enormous observational efforts most studies have concentrated on the local parts of the Galaxy. Few studies go beyond 1 kpc with the exception of some investigations performed in the polar directions. The variation of velocity dispersions, σ_U , σ_V and σ_W , with the distance from the galactic plane, Z , is known to some degree, but for distressingly small samples of stars (a few hundred). The ideal situation must be to sound the Galaxy with probes that are intrinsically identical. The simpler and better known the probes are, the better the Galaxy may be understood. F- and early G-type stars are such simple probes for which relatively accurate photometric distances can be determined, but with the drawback that they are intrinsically rather faint. The accurate proper motions obtained with ROEMER down to the 18th magnitude, combined with the photometric parallaxes, will however remedy the situation and below we outline three specific studies that could be based on such data.

Kinematics of distant F and G stars The proper motions of stars to the 18th magnitude limit of the ROEMER mission allow to deduce the space velocity components U , V , and W over a galactocentric distance interval approaching the ideal demand for galactic models, namely, at least one scale length of the disk, or about 5 kpc. Confining the study to $|Z| \leq 150$ pc and $|b| \leq 5^\circ$ would allow some 12 million main sequence stars from F0 to G3 to have their W velocities determined to better than 20 km s^{-1} , while either the U or the V component could be determined for about a million stars within 5° of the four cardinal directions in the galactic plane. These data will permit a mapping of the space velocities and dispersions over a vast area of the disk from photometrically homogeneous subgroups.

Velocity dispersion and chemistry in the galactic disk ROEMER photometry permits estimating the chemical composition of stars brighter than about $V = 15$. With this limiting magnitude the kinematic variations in the galactic velocity components may be studied for various chemical groups over a range of galactocentric distances from 7.5 to 9.5 kpc. Within $|Z| \leq 150$ pc some 2.5 million F and G stars could be measured. Relative ages could probably be assigned to a substantial fraction of these stars.

Detailed investigation of bright A, F and early G stars at the NGP Within 20° of the north galactic pole we expect some 16,000 F stars, 2400 stars of intermediate population II (thick disk) and several hundred population II (halo) stars brighter than $B = 13.8$. This constitutes a volume complete sample to $Z = 600$ pc, about half the estimated scale height of the thick disk. The sample also includes an estimated 500 A stars. It should be most interesting to obtain kinematic information and parallaxes for these stars whose origin is somewhat of a mystery. Complementary ground-based intermediate $uvby\beta$ (Strömgren) photometry of the A, ipII and pII stars is most important for astrophysical calibrations not least of the unknown luminosities.

2.3.4. *Star clusters and associations*

An accuracy of 0.1 mas yr^{-1} for the proper motions would allow the study of the kinematics of some of the nearest open clusters and OB-associations. In a young open cluster the internal motions are of the order of 1 to 2 km s^{-1} . In older clusters this decreases to only a few hundred m s^{-1} . In associations velocities of several km s^{-1} can be found, reflecting some of the primordial cloud conditions. At a distance of 200 pc, 1 km s^{-1} is equivalent to 1 mas yr^{-1} . Thus, kinematic studies can be done of star clusters within 500 pc and associations within 1500 pc. In contrast to ground-based differential proper motions, the ROEMER proper motion system will also allow studies of contraction and rotation of systems. Comparisons between observed velocity distributions for clusters at different ages and numerical simulations can provide further insights in the dynamical evolution of galactic clusters, and should also show how we could recognize in the phase space distribution function the signature of what once was an open cluster.

In globular clusters the accuracy of proper motions would allow the selection of very large numbers of members, which together with the multi-colour photometry will provide a unique set of empirical isochrones for generally metal-poor stars. As an example, in ω Cen there are 13,000 stars brighter than $B = 17$ resolved at the level of 1 arcsec, covering the HR diagram from the turn-off point upwards.

2.4. Double stars and unseen companions

The ROEMER mission is well suited for the search of close binaries (separations less than 1 arcsec). It will be able to observe 30% of the known binaries, and it is expected that around 100,000 new systems will be discovered among the fainter stars. The very high measuring accuracy will make it possible to detect the positional variations caused by a range of unseen companions, from planets for the nearest stars to so-called brown dwarfs for stars further away. Jupiter-mass planets can potentially be detected around hundreds of stars, brown dwarfs around tens of thousands of target stars. For all these stars very high accuracy parallaxes will also be available. A statistically significant sampling of brown dwarfs and major planets is a crucial programme which permits to obtain relevant constraints on the formation process of stars and planetary systems.

2.5. Solar system objects

Over the last twenty years our knowledge of the Solar System has increased dramatically with the advent of space missions to the planets. A major new exploration of Saturn and its satellites and rings, the Cassini mission, is being planned. Possible missions to Uranus

12 Scientific Objectives

and Neptune are also being studied. Accurate ephemerides for the planets and satellites are essential for the planning of future missions and for the subsequent navigation of the spacecraft. Accurate in this context means about a hundred kilometres which requires observations with a precision of 0.01 arcsec or better.

High-quality observations of the bright satellites of the outer planets, e.g., Callisto for Jupiter, Titan for Saturn, Oberon for Uranus and Triton for Neptune, would enable significant improvements of the ephemerides for these planets. Their faint outer satellites are insufficiently observed from the ground and because of this the long-term behaviour of their orbits cannot be predicted with any great precision. A series of high-quality observations over a few years would be of great value for improving their theories. The most important faint satellites to observe are Hyperion (14th magnitude) and Phoebe (16th magnitude) of Saturn. The theory of the motion of Hyperion is the most complex of any satellite except that of the Moon.

With a limiting magnitude of 18, ROEMER will be able to observe almost all asteroids for which orbits are known with sufficient accuracy—currently several thousand objects. The observing geometry is ideal for improving the orbital parameters and for a determination of a dynamical reference frame, especially for a mission duration of at least 4 years (corresponding to a complete orbit for most of the objects). A comparison of the dynamical reference frame with the kinematically defined extragalactic frame (Section 2.7) is of considerable theoretical and practical value. The five-channel photometry and polarimetry of the asteroids are of great interest for their physical study, especially since the observations cover a much wider range in elongation than is normally accessible from ground.

2.6. General relativity

ROEMER will observe stars at various angular distances from the Sun ranging from $\theta = 35^\circ$ to 145° . The general-relativistic deflection of star light is proportional to $\cot(\theta/2)$ and thus varies between 1 and 13 mas. Considering only the 10^6 stars for which a mean position can be determined to 0.1 mas it is found that the PPN deflection parameter γ could be measured to better than 10^{-4} , or an improvement by at least two orders of magnitude over current determinations. A detailed mapping of the deflection in different directions could put additional constraints on alternative theories. The deflection caused by the Earth is 100 times smaller but could still be determined to about 1% accuracy. This would test general relativity at substantially smaller distance and mass scales than has been possible previously, and for the first time for a body with a significant fraction of neutrons (Gould 1993).

Some of the many billion photometric observations of stars in the Galaxy and the Magellanic Clouds must be affected by gravitational lensing from darker objects closer to us and near to the line of sight. The probability and magnitude of such events should be calculated and a strategy developed for their detection, since it appears that the number and accuracy of observations in the ROEMER mission compares favourably with other planned projects to detect micro-lensing.

Foreground stars could also deflect the light from more distant stars, causing a detectable distortion of the relative proper motion and parallax tracks of optical binaries. The deflection amounts to $4GM/c^2r$, where M is the lensing mass and r the impact parameter. At a distance of 5 pc and one solar mass this translates to 0.5 mas for an angular separation of 3 arcsec. In principle the mass of the foreground star could be derived from such observations.

Fast binary stars, and possibly pulsars, emit gravitational waves which may produce ripples on optical waves propagating past the object (Labeyrie 1993). This would cause an apparent modulation of the luminosity of a background source at twice the binary frequency. If detected such an effect would provide evidence for the existence of gravitational waves, never detected heretofore, and useful verification of theories of gravitation. The modest aperture of ROEMER and the short observing times would however make the possibility of such detection very marginal.

2.7. Reference frame

It is essential for all kinematic studies that proper motions are not biased by large-scale distortions of the reference frame, or by a spurious general rotation. Distortions are minimized by proper design of the mission, allowing large angles to be accurately measured across the whole sky. Absence of a general rotation implies that the proper motions must be referred to a non-rotating (inertial) coordinate system.

It was decided by the International Astronomical Union in 1991 that the astronomical reference frame will in the future be defined by distant extragalactic objects. At present the most accurate realization of this definition involves some four hundred extragalactic radio sources, mainly quasars, observed by VLBI. To transfer this reference to the optical domain will be done, in the first instance, by means of the Hipparcos catalogue. Unfortunately very few (~ 10) objects can be observed both by VLBI and by Hipparcos. Indirect links using the Hubble Space Telescope or photographic plates are also small in number and/or of marginal accuracy. Thus it is not expected to get an accuracy better than 0.5 mas yr^{-1} , possibly worse, for the non-rotation of the Hipparcos optical reference frame.

Proper motions precise to 0.1 mas yr^{-1} , as obtained with ROEMER, imply at least a 20 times better definition of the reference system. The great novelty of this project is however that a very large number of extragalactic objects in the magnitude range 15–16 will be observed together with the programme stars. The determination of the inertial rotation vector of the proper motion system could be based upon 2000 or more such objects ensuring an accuracy of the rotation of better than 0.01 mas yr^{-1} . This represents a gain by a factor of 100 over previous stellar reference frames (FK5 or Hipparcos) and 10 over the best system now achieved by VLBI.

It is also essential for many astrophysical investigations that the positional reference frames in the optical and radio domains agree to a high accuracy. A typical application is when the optical image of a complex source such as SNR1987A is superposed on the corresponding radio map. A physical interpretation of the features requires that the accuracy of the two reference frames is much better than the instrumental resolutions. Thus, with the 100 mas resolution of the Hubble Space Telescope, we require reference systems that agree to about 20 mas. Such accuracy will be provided by Hipparcos, but only for a period of 10 years because of the uncertainty of the proper motions. ROEMER will dramatically extend the useful lifetime of the positional reference frame, and also meet the higher demands that can be expected in the future from optical interferometry.

In establishing the extragalactic link for ROEMER it will be necessary to discuss possible consequences of the proper motion of galaxies and quasars. According to prevalent views, no significant effects are expected. Nevertheless it is worth noting that with ROEMER the systematic measurement accuracy approaches a level that may have cosmological significance—the Hubble constant $H = 100 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ corresponds to 0.02 mas yr^{-1} , if the tangential velocity equals the expansion velocity.

3. Payload Concept

3.1. Basic considerations

The ROEMER concept is derived from the Hipparcos mission (Perryman & Hassan 1989) by taking into account both the positive and negative experiences of that mission, along with considerations of possible enhancements in efficiency and performance by modifications to the basic design. In order to fit into the cost envelope of an ESA Medium Size Mission a reasonable starting point is an instrument of about the same size as that of the Hipparcos payload. For cost reasons as well as light efficiency it is desirable to simplify the optical and mechanical design as much as possible. On the other hand, much higher demands can be tolerated in terms of on-board data storage, computing, and telemetry. From a scientific viewpoint an overall improvement in accuracy and yield by one or more orders of magnitude should be the goal.

The Hipparcos mission has demonstrated the validity of some techniques capable of the required improvement in accuracy and number of stars. It has shown that a beam combiner mirror can provide the very stable angular reference needed. The attitude control system based on cold gas thrusters is suited to give the required long periods of smooth free rotation of the satellite, provided the torques from solar radiation pressure, gyros and structural non-rigidity are decreased.

Hipparcos has also hinted at the enormous photometric potential of a scanning astrometry satellite, provided it is equipped with proper colour filters to define the wavelength bands. The main detector of Hipparcos was not sensitive enough to permit a splitting of the light into several colours. As a result, Hipparcos cannot determine the colours of the faintest stars in its observing programme, for which it must rely on ground-based observations. Such information is needed to eliminate a slight chromaticity of the instrument originating in the colour dispersion of diffraction images.

For the ROEMER mission there are three very strong reasons to incorporate a multi-colour photometric capability for all its observed stars:

- Photometric measurements in (say) five colour bands are scientifically extremely interesting as a complement to the astrometric measurements. An accuracy of the order of 1% (0.01 mag) or better is desirable for astrophysical purposes.
- A colour index must be obtained for all the stars in order to determine and correct for an expected astrometric effect of chromaticity in the optical system. The requirement here is a few percent photometric accuracy.
- The absorption of light in the colour filters will increase the dynamic range of astrometry by permitting the observation of two magnitudes brighter stars before saturation of the detector.

The wavelength bands must be carefully selected to optimize the astrophysical information content of the measurements for different types of objects. In this context the possible use of polarization filters should also be considered.

A high accuracy even at faint magnitudes has obvious advantages, and in fact ROEMER goes five magnitudes fainter than Hipparcos. This is important in order to reach a sufficient number of quasars for establishing an extragalactic reference system and for reaching intrinsically faint stars even at kiloparsec distances. Finally, a large number of stars is required to cover the many different astrophysical purposes and to provide a dense astrometric reference system on the whole sky.

The proposed attitude control for ROEMER uses observations of reference stars for all normal attitude determination and acquisition without use of gyroscopes. If gyros are nevertheless required for special manoeuvres or emergency situations, they should normally be turned off or kept at a low rate. To ensure sufficient mechanical stiffness, the solar panels should be mounted on the satellite surface instead of hinges. The apogee boost motor should be jettisoned after use, lest jitter would arise from the loose solid residue particles inside the chamber.

The detection system is based on CCDs in the focal plane, capable of measuring thousands of stars simultaneously with high quantum efficiency. This replaces the Hipparcos measurement of one star at a time through a modulating grid by a low-efficiency ($\sim 8\%$) image dissector tube. Special purpose CCDs with rectangular pixels can be manufactured today as required to match the precision requirement and the resolving power of the telescope, which differ in the two dimensions. High positional stability is needed even though cooling to -70°C necessarily introduces large temperature differences between the CCDs and their connection to the telescope. A dimensional stability inside a CCD of better than part-per-million, when first-order bulk motion and magnification changes are removed, has been reported by Buffington et al. (1990) for periods of 10 hours. Such stability makes a calibration of CCD irregularities feasible as required for the present purpose.

With a programme of 100 million stars about 4000 stars are observed simultaneously, instead of one star. The quantum efficiency is ten times higher and direct observation in the primary focus is ten times more efficient for astrometry than the Hipparcos modulating grid. Thus, the proposed CCD system provides at least 100,000 times higher astrometric efficiency than Hipparcos with the same telescope aperture.

3.2. Detection system

In the focal plane of a scanning satellite like Hipparcos or ROEMER all stars move in almost parallel tracks ‘along scan’. The direction and speed of the apparent motion of the star images must be constant to within a fraction of a percent, and the actual values as functions of time must be known within 10^{-4} , which is feasible. The very accurate astrometric measurements are only made in the direction along the scan, not perpendicularly, the reason being that the beam combiner is an accurate standard of large angles only in the plane spanned by the two mirror normals, i.e., along the scan.

The focal plane measuring device may accordingly consist of long modulating slits perpendicular to the scan direction, as in Hipparcos, or of *rectangular* CCD pixels (Figure 1b). A pixel width of $w = 0.18$ arcsec in the direction of scan will match the optical resolution of a telescope with aperture $D = 0.336$ m. Since $4\ \mu\text{m}$ is the smallest width of pixel that we can hope to have manufactured, a focal length of about $f = 4.7$ m is desirable, implying a focal ratio of $f/D = 14$. The high focal ratio is advantageous in terms of aberrations, straylight suppression and alignment requirements, but also gives a rather large central obscuration in a centred optical system.

The detector system in Figure 1a consists of 20 identical CCD chips, each containing a narrow and a wide CCD. All CCDs are used for high precision astrometry and photometry. A narrow CCD contains 256×64 pixels and a wide contains 4096×1024 pixels of rectangular forms as shown in Figure 1b. A ‘drift-scan’ integration of the star image takes place while the image is moving across a CCD: when it has moved the distance $w/3$ (which takes about

Figure 1. Focal plane arrangement of ROEMER. a: The stars drift across 20 chips, each containing a narrow and a wide CCD. Reading of the number of accumulated electrons (counts) takes place in a special register at the right edge of each CCD. Eight of the chips, at left and right, measure in a wide spectral band *W* and twelve in the photometric bands *UBVRI* and, perhaps, in polarized light (*P-*, *P+*). b: The rectangular pixels. c: A star record of 16 samples.

0.33 ms) all charges of the CCD are quickly shifted by one-third pixel in the direction of the image drift. Provided that the shift rate is adequately tuned to the speed of the optical images, the charge images are thus only smeared by one-third of a pixel width. When the charges have been shifted by a whole pixel width, the accumulated charges are read out from a reading register at the right edge of each CCD. The narrow CCDs are used for bright stars, where the longer integration times on the wide CCDs would saturate the charge images, and for attitude acquisition.

In the layout of Figure 1a eight of the chips measure the light in a wide spectral band *W* and ten in the photometric bands *UBVRI*. Two chips marked *P-* and *P+* may be used for polarization measurements, or may be provided with additional *U* filters if this is considered more useful. The choice and layout of filters is of course a matter that will require careful consideration.

A star image as recorded by a CCD is schematically shown in Figure 1c. The charges in four vertical pixels are usually added, giving one sample per 1.0 ms per star. Any star in the input catalogue should be covered by about 16 samples, assuming rms errors of 0.25 arcsec for the positions in the input catalogue and 0.1 arcsec for the real time attitude knowledge. Each of the samples corresponds to 4.2 s integration during the crossing of a wide CCD. With an observing programme of 100 million stars the data rate from 20 wide and 20 narrow CCDs amounts to 25,000 samples s^{-1} which must be transmitted to the ground together with timing information etc.

Figure 2. The focal plane behind a flat folding mirror. (A-A) The CCDs remain unvignetted by the circular hole in the mirror, corresponding to a central obscuration ratio of 0.40.

The length of the pixels perpendicular to the scan direction is uncritical for the accurate along-scan measurement. But measurements perpendicular to the scan are still required for bright reference stars in order to determine the three-axis attitude of the spacecraft. On the wide CCDs the pixel length is $h = 0.72$ arcsec which will allow the perpendicular coordinates of the reference stars to be determined with a precision of 0.1 arcsec if all four pixels in a vertical column are read for all bright reference stars. This precision is sufficient for the required attitude determination in real time and on ground, thus eliminating the need for a special starmapper detector as in Hipparcos. For the subsequent data reduction on ground the three-axis attitude need to be determined to about 0.01 arcsec accuracy, which is feasible with about one million reference stars available.

The CCD chips are mounted on a frame of high thermal dimensional stability. Their surface shall follow the focal surface, taking into account the optical thicknesses of the twelve colour filters. The wide CCDs in the W band will permit linear accumulation of charge only for stars fainter than $V = 13$. The narrow CCDs will be linear up to $V = 7$ in the W band, and up to $V = 4$ or 5 behind a colour filter. These limits are expected because the linearity of present-day CCD pixels ends at 15,000 electrons per $100 \mu\text{m}^2$, while a star of $V = 10$ will produce 95,000 electrons s^{-1} , nearly half of them sometimes in one pixel. Saturation occurs at a three times higher charge. These estimates may be pessimistic as future CCD techniques are expected to permit ten times higher charge densities.

Figure 3. Optical system with focal length 4700 mm and aperture diameter 336 mm. The beam combiner mirror BC has a basic angle of (say) 54.5° . A telescope with two flat folding mirrors, FM1 and FM2, and the primary mirror PM, can be placed in a cylindrical spacecraft of 3000 mm diameter.

3.3. Optical system

The desirable focal length of 4.7 m derived in Section 3.2 is much longer than the 1.4 m of Hipparcos so that a rather different optical system is needed. A field diameter of about one degree is required in order to cover the sky with the same 'revolving' pattern as Hipparcos. A field of this diameter can be accommodated without vignetting in the telescope shown in Figures 2 and 3 having a central obscuration ratio of 0.40. The telescope is of the Wright-Väisälä type where the surface of the beam combiner is slightly deformed. This differs from a classical Schmidt system (as used for Hipparcos) in that the corrector plate, or in this case the beam combiner, is not placed at the curvature centre of the primary mirror, but nearer to the primary, which must then be ellipsoidal to eliminate coma. The total (unfolded) length of the system is thus reduced from twice the focal length for a Schmidt telescope to about 1.3 times the focal length in this case. The maximum deformations of the beam combiner and the primary mirror are about 50 and 500 nm, respectively. Diffraction-limited performance is obtained in the required field which has zero curvature.

A beam combiner of the same type as used for Hipparcos provides the very stable large-angle reference needed to perform global astrometry. The beam combiner splits the telescope aperture in equal halves, producing two superposed fields of view at the focal surface. The angular separation of the two fields, the 'basic angle', equals twice the (acute) angle between the beam combiner surfaces. The precise value of the basic angle is determined as part of the routine data processing from the 360° closure condition of a complete revolution

of the instrument about its spin axis. Since the spin period is 2 hours, an angular stability of the order of 0.2 mas is required on time scales of a few hours. Preliminary results from the Hipparcos analysis indicate that such a stability may already be achieved in that project, although the time resolution and accuracy of the basic angle determinations are not sufficient to deduce the short-term behaviour with certainty. The long-term drift of the Hipparcos basic angle is less than 0.1 mas per day (Schrijver & van der Marel 1992). Thus we do not consider the beam combiner to require additional technological development (cf. Section 4.3).

The accuracy with which the angles of stars can be determined along a great-circle scan depends on the size of the basic angle and of the field of view, and on the number and accuracy of elementary stellar measurements. The basic angle chosen for Hipparcos was 58° . In retrospect it would seem that this value is uncomfortably close to $1/6$ of a revolution, thus rendering it more difficult to determine those components of the stellar positions which correspond to a wave of period 60° along the scanning circles. While the systematic effects of this phenomenon can be eliminated in the reductions, there is nevertheless a residual part, or 'non-rigidity' of the great-circle system of equations, which contributes significantly to the random error of all stars (cf. Perryman & Hassan 1989, Section 3.6). The effect can be reduced by choosing a slightly different value for the basic angle, say 54.5° . A study by Makarov et al. (1992) indicates that the non-rigidity effect is further reduced to a negligible level if as many as the one million brightest stars on the sky are included in the great-circle reductions.

3.4. Consequences for the spacecraft design

A very smooth rotation of the satellite is desirable for deriving the three-axis attitude to the required accuracy of 0.01 arcsec, ten times better than the requirement for Hipparcos. The main torques disturbing a purely inertial rotation of Hipparcos at the geostationary distance are solar radiation pressure and reactions of the gyroscopes (used for measuring the attitude) generated by the satellite spin. The resulting attitude perturbations have to be compensated by firing of gas jets about every 10 minutes in Hipparcos in order to maintain the attitude within the required limits, whereas a purely inertial rotation would require much less frequent firings.

The interval between firings should be increased to at least 30 minutes, corresponding to about 90° of free satellite rotation. This means that the perturbing torques just mentioned must be decreased to one tenth of their value for Hipparcos. Other torques, e.g. from gravity gradient and the magnetic field, are still smaller. The solar radiation torque can be decreased by giving the satellite nearly rotational symmetry (cf. drawing on front cover page) and such form, surface and mass distribution that the resultant solar pressure vector goes nearly through the center of mass. The gyro reaction torque can be sufficiently reduced by having the gyroscopes spinning at reduced rate during nominal operation when they are not needed.

The nominal revolving scanning law of Hipparcos should in principle be maintained For ROEMER. Simulation studies have shown that it is difficult to improve on the revolving scanning concept in terms of sky coverage and homogeneity of the resulting astrometric determinations. However, the constant 'revolving angle' between the satellite spin axis and the direction to the Sun is a free parameter in this scanning law. For the Hipparcos mission straylight and power considerations limited this angle to 43° . A somewhat larger value of 55° will give a more uniform accuracy over the sky and more precise parallaxes.

Solar panels are placed on the upper circular surface in Figure 3. The available area (7 m^2) is slightly larger than the sum of the three solar panels of Hipparcos. Panels on hinges should in any case be avoided for better overall stiffness of the mechanical structure.

3.5. Towards 10 micro-arcsec astrometry: The FIZEAU option

This section, not part of the baseline (ROEMER) proposal, is included to point out a possible development towards a scanning satellite with ten times the angular accuracy of ROEMER. The scientific benefits of such an accuracy for many millions of stars are enormous: may it suffice to point out that it would permit a direct spatial and kinematic mapping of the greater part of our Galaxy, its halo and the immediate extragalactic neighbourhood including the Magellanic Clouds.

A natural extension of the ROEMER concept is a scanning double interferometer with viewing directions separated by a large and fixed angle. The tenfold increase in accuracy would be obtained already with a modest baseline of about 3 m. The concept considered here is due to A. Labeyrie and consists of two confocal Fizeau-type (or 'wide field') interferometers whose axes form a basic angle of the order of 140° (Figure 4). Each interferometer is formed by two small ($\sim 30 \text{ cm}$) segments of a single large paraboloidal mirror. The fixed angle is maintained by the two optical blocks formed by the mirror segments at the intersections of the paraboloids. A small Cassegrain secondary relays the common focus to a CCD sensor. The sensitive elements are thus mounted in three separate optical blocks which can be contained in a tubular truss with a total length of about 4 m. In contrast with for instance the POINTS concept the confocal paraboloidal scheme avoids the errors caused by structural truss flexure, which here has no first-order effect on the angular measurements. What must be controlled is the ratio of the arm lengths, but passive control is probably adequate with materials such as zero-expansion graphite-epoxy for the truss structure.

The focal image is an Airy disc containing $N = L/D$ fringes, where D is the diameter of the apertures and L their spacing. With a wide spectral window only the central (white) fringe is sharp and carries most of the astrometric information. Fourier transformation of the whole interferogram provides multi-colour photometry with a spectral resolution corresponding to the fringe count. The fringe pattern is field invariant to first order but are in reality affected by the field aberrations of the Cassegrain system. A very serious practical difficulty is to ensure enough usable field in both directions observed: the off-axis paraboloidal mirror segments have very strong coma and astigmatism. The coma may be corrected by distorting the mirrors in Ritchey-Crétien fashion, but ray-tracing calculations are needed to determine what further corrective elements may be required.

The optical sensor may consist of a group of CCD detectors operating in the continuous scanning mode, similar to what is proposed for ROEMER. The number of pixels required to keep the same field in the scanning direction is however multiplied by $L/D = 10$. Since this number also represents the basic gain in angular resolution, it may instead be preferable to sacrifice the field width in the scanning direction and use fewer pixels. The operating philosophy and the data reductions remain to be defined but could be similar to those of the Hipparcos and ROEMER projects. In particular the main instrument parameters such as the basic angle of 140° must be determined from the closure conditions on the great-circle scans, which would essentially eliminate the need for complicated calibration and metrology equipment.

Figure 4. Optical sketch of a Fizeau-type scanning interferometer. The beam combiners are part of a pair of confocal paraboloids (P' , P'') whose axes A' and A'' make a fixed angle of approx 140° .

4. Mission and System Aspects

4.1. Predicted performance

The following estimate of the astrometric and photometric mean errors for the ROEMER mission is based on photon-statistical errors, since it is expected that the other significant errors in Hipparcos from 'non-rigidity' and from parasitic stars can be neglected in ROEMER (cf. Section 3.3). The measurement of a programme star could be disturbed if another 'parasitic' star is situated within about 6×4 pixels = 3.0 arcsec^2 centered on the programme star (cf. Figure 1c). The probability of having a star brighter than $V = 21$ within this area in either field-of-view is 0.024 for the mean sky and 0.10 if both fields are in the galactic plane. Therefore, parasitic stars will give negligible disturbance in astrometry and photometry, compared with photon noise.

Predicted mean errors for a 2.5 year ROEMER mission are given in Table 2. The table is based on the following assumptions:

- stars are of spectral type G0 and visual magnitudes V as shown in the first column;
- the nominal mission length is 2.5 years;
- the fractional dead time due to Earth occultations amounts to 10%;

22 Mission and System Aspects

Table 2. Predicted mean errors in astrometry and photometry for a 2.5 year ROEMER mission. Columns 2 and 3 give errors for parallax and annual proper motions in milli-arcsec (mas), but asymptotic errors should be added as discussed in the text. Photometric errors refer to a star of spectral type G0 and are given in the wide W band from 300–950 nm, and in five standard photometric wavelength bands $UBVRI$.

V [mag]	Astrometry		Photometry (W = wide band)					
	parallax [mas]	proper motion [mas yr ⁻¹]	W [mag]	U [mag]	B [mag]	V [mag]	R [mag]	I [mag]
11	0.08	0.09	0.001	0.003	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001
12	0.12	0.14	0.001	0.005	0.002	0.002	0.001	0.001
13	0.19	0.22	0.001	0.008	0.003	0.002	0.002	0.002
14	0.30	0.35	0.001	0.013	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.004
15	0.48	0.56	0.001	0.022	0.007	0.006	0.006	0.006
16	0.77	0.91	0.002	0.037	0.011	0.010	0.009	0.010
17	1.29	1.50	0.004	0.069	0.018	0.016	0.015	0.016
18	2.25	2.63	0.006	—	0.032	0.028	0.026	0.028

- the beam combiner aperture is $D = 0.336$ m;
- the focal length is $f = 4.7$ m;
- mirror spectral reflectances are taken from Perryman & Hassan (1989), Table 5.2;
- the colour filter passbands are according to Bessell (1990);
- the quantum efficiency of the thinned back-illuminated CCDs is 0.56, 0.80, 0.65, 0.42 at 300, 650, 800, 900 nm wavelength, respectively;
- a background of 20 (equivalent e^-) counts per sample is assumed, as expected from a read noise of $2e^-$, plus sky and straylight as in the Hipparcos requirements (corresponding to one star of $V = 20.3$, $B - V = 0.7$ per arcsec²);
- the scanning speed is 170 arcsec s⁻¹ giving 14.4 crossings star⁻¹ yr⁻¹ CCD⁻¹;
- the charge image is smeared due to the pixel width (0.18 arcsec), the relative uncertainty of 10^{-4} in the real-time knowledge of scanning speed, the 1/3-pixel shifting and the discrete sampling;
- four samples around the peak of each star image are used for estimation;
- a margin factor of 1.2 is applied to all photon noise errors, both for astrometry and photometry.

The equivalent photoelectron rate for a star of magnitude $V = 10$ is 95,000 Hz in the wide W band, to be compared with the 600 Hz predicted for Hipparcos (Perryman et al. 1989, Eq. [12.3]) and the observed rate of 730 Hz early in the orbit. The increase by more than a factor 100 is explained mainly by the higher quantum efficiency (10 $\times$), the wider wavelength band (2 $\times$), and the absence of a modulating grid and relay optics (5 $\times$).

The mean errors given in Table 2 will be too optimistic for the bright stars. An asymptotic mean error must be added, especially to the astrometric errors. This is very difficult to estimate, but based on the experiences with Hipparcos data, asymptotic errors of 0.1 mas for the parallaxes, positions and annual proper motions would seem conservative.

If some of the assumptions listed above must be modified for technological or cost reasons, the performance figures in Table 2 can be scaled according to the following considerations:

1. The assumed pixel width of $4\ \mu\text{m}$ may be too small to manufacture. If it is increased to $6\ \mu\text{m}$, all astrometric errors should be multiplied by 1.23, while the photometry is almost unaffected.
2. A focal length of 4.7 m requires two folding mirrors whereas $f = 2.6\ \text{m}$ with only one folding mirror would be less expensive. With this modification the astrometric errors should be multiplied by 1.34; again the photometric errors are practically unaffected.
3. A combination of 1. and 2. would require a correction factor of 1.52 on the astrometry.
4. On the other hand an extension of the mission length from 2.5 to five years could be considered. This would imply a factor 0.7 on the mean errors in position, parallax and photometry, and a factor 0.35 in proper motion.

4.2. Mission requirements

This section summarizes the main requirements on mission design.

Orbit The ROEMER satellite should be launched into a geostationary position. Continuous contact with a ground station is essential because of the high-rate, continuous stream of science data which cannot be buffered on-board for any length of time. Also, since the systematic sky scanning is indifferent to the position of the Earth, interruptions will occur whenever the Earth comes into one of the fields of view. The total dead time due to such occultations is minimized in a high (i.e., geostationary) orbit.

The geocentric position and velocity vectors of the satellite need to be known in order to process the science data correctly. The requirement in position is $\sim 100\ \text{m}$ (as set by the observation of solar-system objects), while the velocity is needed to about $0.02\ \text{m s}^{-1}$ in order to correct for the aberration of light. These requirements could easily be met with an on-board GPS receiver.

Lifetime The performance figures and scientific objectives are based on a nominal lifetime of 2.5 years. Consumables should be sized for a potential lifetime of at least 5 years.

Telemetry The downlink telemetry rate is estimated to $50\ \text{kbytes s}^{-1}$. Unless the whole input catalogue of 100 million stars can be permanently stored on-board (which seems unlikely), chunks of it need to be uplinked at regular intervals. The mean uplink data rate is about $1\ \text{kbytes s}^{-1}$.

Timing The principle of measurement translates the timing of CCD samples into relative positions in the focal plane, using the smooth rotation of the satellite, at $170\ \text{arcsec s}^{-1}$, as a short-term reference. To ensure a potential accuracy of 0.1 mas in the relative measurements, provisions are needed which enable a time tagging of data samples with a precision of $0.5\ \mu\text{s}$ or better relative to the on-board clock. This clock in turn must be related to the astronomical time scales (such as UTC) with an absolute accuracy of about 0.1 ms, as required for the observation of the fastest-moving solar-system objects.

4.3. Technological development requirements

We have identified the following areas as particularly critical and potentially requiring some technological development:

1. CCD detectors: noise and stability. Low dark and readout noise and high geometric/photometric stability are fundamental to the sensitivity and accuracy of the mission. In particular the transient and permanent effects of radiation and possible after-effects of the strong optical and infrared illumination by the Earth need to be evaluated.
2. Mounting and cooling of CCDs: the CCDs should be operated at about 200 K in order to give an acceptable dark current. On the other hand, given the thermal expansion coefficient of silicon, the temperature of the chips must be controlled to about 0.01 K over several hours in order to maintain dimensional stability to ± 0.1 mas. The mounting of individual chips (bonded to metal plates with the same thermal expansion coefficient as the silicon substrate?), the connection of the 20 CCDs in a larger frame (of ultra-low expansion coefficient?), and the cooling and temperature regulation system are particularly critical items.
3. Colour filters: types (dye/interference filters), materials, homogeneity, flatness, mounting, thermal properties, long-term effects of radiation?
4. Attitude control and determination: the perturbing torques have to be reduced by an order of magnitude compared with Hipparcos. This affects the mass distribution and exterior design of the satellite, mounting of the solar panels and the operation of gyros, but would hardly require technological development.
5. Beam combiner: the Hipparcos mission has demonstrated a very high angular stability of this component, possibly to a level sufficient even for ROEMER. Given its central role as an angular reference, the beam combiner and its thermal control are still critical items. However we do not consider that they require any additional technological development.
6. Telescope mirrors: a progressive deformation of one of the mirrors in Hipparcos has been observed, probably related to the abnormal radiation environment experienced in that mission. The causes and remedies of the effect should be investigated so that a similar deterioration can be avoided for ROEMER.

4.4. Mass budget

The cost limit for a Medium Size Mission practically implies a maximum total launch weight of about 1100 kg. Of this, some 500 kg solid propellant is needed to inject the satellite into a geostationary orbit, including the apogee boost motor. This leaves about 600 kg for the spacecraft and payload, which is about the same as for Hipparcos. The much longer focal length of the ROEMER telescope requires a satellite diameter of 3.0 m (Figure 3), or about 40% larger than Hipparcos excluding solar panels. In spite of the larger linear dimensions of the payload it should nevertheless be possible to keep almost the same mass since most of the heavy and complicated focal-plane assembly of Hipparcos will not be needed in ROEMER. The high focal ratio of ROEMER should relax the requirements for optical alignment; combined with the use of thin or super-lightweighted mirrors this should permit a significantly lighter payload structure in relation to its volume.

A tentative mass budget is shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Mass budget for the ROEMER satellite.

Element	Mass (kg)
Payload	215
structure	100
optics	50
baffles	20
thermal control	15
detection system	10
harness	10
miscellaneous	10
Spacecraft	425
structure	120
electrical power	100
attitude and orbit control	60
data handling	40
harness	40
telecommunications	10
GPS	10
cold gas	10
miscellaneous	35
Mass in geostationary orbit	640
Apogee boost motor and propellant	500
Total launch mass	1140

5. Science operations, data reductions and archiving

A high level of involvement of scientific institutes is required in order to prepare the observing programme, to assist in the monitoring and calibration of the payload, and to perform the data reductions. An organization similar to that of the Hipparcos project is appropriate, i.e., that at least two different ‘scientific consortia’ are formed, one for the preparation of the observing programme and the other for the data reductions.

The observing programme (or ‘input catalogue’), in order to satisfy statistical sampling requirements, should be drawn from a complete stellar inventory of the sky to a limiting magnitude of $V = 18$ (about 400 million objects). A combination of digitised photographic sky surveys now available or under construction will provide a convenient base for constructing the fainter part of the programme, while data for brighter stars ($V < 12$) will come mainly from the Hipparcos and Tycho catalogues. The scientific community should be invited to propose specific targets in the magnitude range $15 < V < 18$. The required 0.25 arcsec accuracy of the input catalogue at the epoch 2005 can be achieved from photographic sky surveys by using Hipparcos and Tycho stars as a reference. An option to

operate ROEMER without an input catalogue, except for a few million bright reference stars and selected faint objects, should also be studied. This would instead require on-board, quasi-real-time detection of images in order to pick out and transmit the relevant pixels.

During nominal operation the scientific mission support required from the operations centre includes extraction, pre-processing and uplinking of the relevant parts of the input catalogue; reception, time-tagging, monitoring and formatting of telemetry data; orbit determination; and the distribution and archiving of raw science data. The initial phases will also include the provisional calibration of parameters necessary for the nominal operations, such as scale values and basic angle. Note however that the precise calibrations as required for the astrometric and photometric processing are part of the normal scientific data reductions.

The data reductions for the ROEMER mission will be much larger in pure quantity than the Hipparcos/Tycho reductions, but in several ways it will be less complicated. This is mainly due to the fact that there is only one kind of detector and it observes the direct star images instead of modulated signals. The reductions will basically consist of the following steps:

1. local analysis of the detector signals: background determination, image location, signal amplitudes, statistical indices;
2. attitude determination;
3. reduction of star positions on a reference great circle, calibration of geometric and photometric instrument parameters;
4. combination of great-circle results in a full-sky solution.

Step 1 will only be done once for all the stars, while step 2 to 4 are made iteratively for a subset of ~ 1 million primary stars. This will establish a set of instrument calibrations and a rigid reference frame over the whole sky enabling the final step to be carried out, viz.,

5. astrometric and photometric tie-in of the remaining objects.

For 100 million programme stars the data rate of raw observations is about 50 kbytes s^{-1} or 4000 Gbytes in 2.5 years. Because of the global nature of the reductions we do not foresee that it would be useful to keep the raw data available as a data base. They may be stored on optical tapes for safety and longevity, but it is not likely that they would ever be needed again unless some unexpected new use of the data would emerge.

The resulting astrometric and photometric catalogue of 100 million objects cannot be printed but should be distributed on CD ROMs or similar high-density media. In addition an on-line data base facility should be established either under the ESA Science Programme or at an independent institute. The size of the catalogue would be about 20 Gbytes.

6. Management and Funding

The operating principle of the ROEMER satellite implies a high degree of interdependence between the payload and spacecraft. In particular, the payload instrument is the only attitude sensor used in the normal operation mode; conversely, the real-time attitude determination drives both the three-axis attitude control by gas thrusters and the extraction of science data from the detection system. Another feature which distinguishes ROEMER from other observatory-type satellites like ISO or XMM is that the payload consists of a single instrument, an integrated unit of baffles, beam combiner, telescope and detection system.

It is proposed that the European Space Agency takes the overall responsibility for the design, management and manufacture of both payload and spacecraft. We have not identified any national institutes or agencies that could assume responsibility for the management and funding of the scientific instrument as a whole. This does not preclude that such sponsoring can be found for subsystem elements such as mirrors, filters and detectors.

National funding will be sought for the participation of scientists and institutes in the preparation of the observing programme (input catalogue) and for the data reductions. These tasks are estimated to be of a size similar to the corresponding tasks within the Hipparcos project. External funding should also be considered for the archiving of the resulting astrometric and photometric catalogues at one or several science institutes.

7. References

- Allen, C.W. 1973, *Astrophysical Quantities*, 3rd edition, Athlone Press, London
- Bessell M.S. 1990, Publications of the Astronomical Society of the Pacific, 102, 1181
- Buffington A., Hudson H.S., Booth C.H. 1990, Publications of the Astronomical Society of the Pacific, 102, 688
- Gould A. 1993, *Deflection of Light by the Earth*, Astrophysics Preprint Series IASSNS-AST 93/5, Institute for Advanced Study, Princeton
- Høg E. 1992, *Astrometry and Photometry of 400 Million Stars Brighter Than 18 Mag.* In 'Developments in Astrometry and their Impacts on Astrophysics and Geodynamics', Proc. IAU Symp. No. 156, I.I. Mueller and B. Kolaczek (eds.), Kluwer Academic Publishers, Dordrecht (in press)
- Labeyrie A. 1993, *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 268, 823
- Makarov V., Høg E., Lindegren L. 1992, *Accuracy of Star Abscissae in the Rømer Project*, internal report, Copenhagen University Observatory
- Perryman M.A.C., Hassan H. 1989, *The Hipparcos Mission, Volume I, The Hipparcos Satellite*. ESA Publications Division, ESA SP-1111
- Perryman M.A.C., Lindegren L., Murray C.A., Høg E., Kovalevsky J. 1989, *The Hipparcos Mission, Volume III, The Data Reductions*. ESA Publications Division, ESA SP-1111
- Perryman M.A.C., Høg E., Kovalevsky J., Lindegren L., Turon C., Bernacca P.L., Crézé M., Donati F., Grenon M., Grewing M., van Leeuwen F., van der Marel H., Murray C.A., Le Poole R.S., Schrijver H. 1992, *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 258, 1
- Schrijver H., van der Marel H. 1992, *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 258, 31

List of Proposers

Høg, E.	Copenhagen University Observatory (DK)
Kovalevsky, J.	Observatoire de la Côte d'Azur, Grasse (F)
van Leeuwen, F.	Royal Greenwich Observatory, Cambridge (UK)
Lindgren, L.	Lund Observatory (S)
Bastian, U.	Astronomisches Rechen-Institut, Heidelberg (FRG)
Gilmore, G.	Royal Greenwich Observatory, Cambridge (UK)
Halbwachs, J.L.	Observatoire de Strasbourg (F)
Knude, J.	Copenhagen University Observatory (DK)
Labeyrie, A.	Observatoire de la Côte d'Azur, Grasse (F)
Pel, J.W.	Kapteyn Sterrewacht, Roden (NL)
Schrijver, J.H.	SRON Space Research Utrecht (NL)
Stabell, R.	Institute of Theoretical Astrophysics, Oslo (N)
Thejll, P.	Niels Bohr Institute, Copenhagen (DK)

Acknowledgement

We are grateful for discussions and technical support provided by K. Clausen, R. Florentin Nielsen, J.M. Beckers, S. Frandsen, D. Heger, V.V. Makarov, K. Mattila, K.P. Moesgaard, I.D. Novikov, M.A.C. Perryman, C.S. Petersen, J.O. Petersen, A.G. Polnarev, S. Refsdal, D. Taylor, C. Thykier, K. Wagner, A. Wicnec, and R.N. Wilson.